

Interduodenal Pancreatic-Caval Tumour Mass: Paraganglioma

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Abstract

Non-functional retroperitoneal paragangliomas are rare tumors arising from extraprestinal chromaffin tissue. They are often asymptomatic and can grow to large dimensions, and their diagnosis and surgical management can be difficult. Treatment requires complete surgical excision. We report the case of a 56-year-old patient who presented with epigastric pain. Histological examination of the mass revealed a paraganglioma, a retroperitoneal tumor.

Introduction

Paraganglioma is an endocrine tumor that develops chromaffin cells [1]. The retroperitoneal forms are less frequent than other localizations [2,3]. Positive diagnosis requires plasma and urine hormone assays. Imaging and isotopic explorations are essential prior to surgery. Surgery is the only curative therapeutic option. It must be combined with prevention and monitoring of hemodynamic and cardiovascular disorders. Prognosis depends on the metastatic nature of the tumour and the presence of post-operative tumour residue. Genetic testing is recommended; recurrence and association with other tumors are more common in reported in genetic forms.

Case Report

A 63-year-old hypertensive patient, treated for pulmonary TBK 3 years ago, presented with chronic epigastralgia, without vomiting, externalized digestive haemorrhage or jaundice. Moreover, the symptoms had worsened 6 months ago with a sensation of heaviness in the right hypochondrium in a context of deterioration in general condition. On examination, patient conscious 15/15, haemodynamically and respiratorily stable, conjunctiva normocoloured, abdominal examination supple abdomen, no palpable mass, rectal examination unremarkable. Abdominal

and pelvic CT scan (figure 1) showed an oval retroperitoneal lesion, inter pancreatico-duodeno-caval, of solid cystic nature, measuring 34/33 mm, extended over 42 mm in height, with a moderately raised fleshy component and nourishing ramifications emanating from the gastro-duodenal arch and the aorta.

Figure 1: CT Solid Cystic Mass Interduodeno
Pancreato Cava

More Information

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Keywords:

paraganglioma, mass, retroperitoneal, tumor, surgery.

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It lies against the medial side of the second duodenal portion and the inferior genu, without any notable thickening or endoluminal bud. It is surrounded by an incomplete fatty separation line with the uncus of the pancreas and the TP. Intimate contact with the permeable right renal artery and IVC. Abdominal MRI (figure2) objectified a well circumscribed complex inter duodeno-pancreato-caval cystic formation measures 34x33 mm. echo endoscopy finds normal gastrointestinal tract, mild compression aspect at antral region normal papilla with Presence of cystic lesion.

Figure 2: MRI Interduodeno Pancreato Cystic Mass

Figure 3: Exploration of the Retro Duodeno Pacreatic Mass

Multilocular of 40mm/ 38mm, well limited, at the niveau of the spaces with an intimate relationship with the pancreas head, the posterior aspect of the duodenum, and the VBP which is not dilated. The procedure consisted of resection of a cystic mass between the duodenum and pancreas, retrograde cholecystectomy and subhepatic drainage using a salem probe, with no peritoneal effusion on examination, no nodules of carcinosis, no hepatic metastases, thin-walled lithiasis of the gallbladder,

presence of a cystic mass with a long axis of 4 cm between the duodenum and the pancreatic cavity after kocher detachment (figure 3).

Histological examination of the samples revealed a poorly differentiated tumour proliferation encapsulated in a thin fibrous capsule. The final immunohistochemical diagnosis was poorly differentiated tumour proliferation in favour of a paraganglioma.

Figure 4: Surgical Part of the Mass

Discussion

Paraganglioma is a rare entity, sharing the same clinical presentation as pheochromocytomas, composed of chromaffin cells which can secrete catecholamines. which can secrete catecholamines. Retroperitoneal paragangliomas are a rare entity. They can occur at any age, most often in young adults [4,5]. Functional symptoms are related to catecholamine secretion [4]. The main symptom is arterial hypertension. All three symptoms - headache, palpitations and profuse sweating - are present in around 90% of cases [6,7] Others are less suggestive: abdominal pain, anxiety, chills, pallor and digestive problems [6]. Positive diagnosis of chromaffin cell tumours is based on hormone assays. Measurement of free plasma metanephrines or fractionated metanephrines in urine identifies most cases of paragangliomas. A recent evaluation by a German laboratory suggests that first morning spot urine provides an accurate measurement and may be considered a more practical option than 24-hour urine collection [8]. Urinary normetanephrines and plasma chromogranin A correlate with tumour mass and risk of progression [9]. CT is equivalent to MRI in tumour localisation but is less competitive in the differential diagnosis with other tumours [1]. CT can show a typically solid, round, homogeneous retroperitoneal and retroduodenal mass, sometimes with necrotic or cystic areas in the centre of the tumour

[9]. This is almost the same case as our patient, in whom the CT scan showed a round interduodenal solidocystic mass [10]. Metastatic tumours, extra-adrenal tumours and tumours with multiple sites are best investigated by MIBG scintigraphy; even small sites without pathological fixation [11]. Paragangliomas are known to be more aggressive than pheochromocytomas. Malignancy, defined by the presence of metastases, occurs in 10 to 15% of cases. Metastatic lesions are generally found in the lungs, liver, spleen and skeleton [12]. They are mainly suspected when the tumour weighs more than 80g, or when it is described on imaging as a heterogeneous mass with irregular margins [13]. The management of paragangliomas requires a multidisciplinary approach. Surgery is the only curative treatment, provided it is complete [8,14]. Survival rates are 75% and 45% at 5 and 10 years respectively [15,16]. Because of the vascularisation of these tumours, some authors recommend preoperative embolisation of the tumour [17]. In our patient, although the tumour was in close contact with the inferior vena cava, resection was complete. Other authors prefer laparoscopic resection of paragangliomas with all the known advantages of minimally invasive surgery [18]. When surgery is not an option, palliative medical treatment is considered. Chemotherapy and high-dose I-MIBG radionuclide therapy have been tried. Larger studies are needed to better assess efficacy and disease control [19,20]. According to the recommendations of the Task Force (2014), all patients with paraganglioma should undergo a genetic study. The mutations identified are found in 30% of cases [21]. The most common is the succinate dehydrogenase (SDH) mutation; the subunit B (SDH-B) mutation is found in 40% of metastatic paragangliomas [22]. Other less frequent mutations have been mentioned, such as the HIF-2A mutation, observed in the association of polycythemia with paraganglioma [23]. Histological studies are unreliable in determining whether the tumour is benign or malignant [15,17,24]. Until now, some authors have considered that there were no histological criteria for malignancy and that it was the appearance of distant metastases during the patient's follow-up that confirmed the malignancy of the paraganglioma [15,17]. Despite studies of pleomorphism, mitotic activity or vascular invasion of the tumour, the evolution is unpredictable. Immunohistochemical studies on the aggressiveness of these tumours are underway. Prognosis may depend on the extent of expression of certain neuropeptides (Ki-67, Bax, and Bcl-2 and S-100 protein) [24].

Conclusion

Paragangliomas are rare tumours, most often seen in young adults. They may be asymptomatic for a long time and therefore be diagnosed at a late stage. Knowledge of the clinical symptoms is necessary to

make the diagnosis of a chromaffin cell tumour. Hormone assays provide a positive diagnosis, and recent studies have shown interesting results with more specific methods and biomarkers. Physicians should bear in mind the possibility of extra-adrenal sites, which are best identified by MIBG scintigraphy. Histology is often not useful in determining the benign or malignant nature of the tumour. Follow-up of patients is therefore necessary. Surgical treatment is the only radical treatment and should be performed even in paragangliomas in close contact with the great vessels.

Declaration for Human Participants

This study has been approved by the head of the Department of General surgery of the IBN ROCHD University Hospital of Casablanca, Hassan II University of Casablanca, and the principles of the Helsinki Declaration were followed.

Conflict of Interest

The authors reported no conflict of interest.

Data Availability

All data are included in the content of the paper.

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